

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF INDIVIDUAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6535673>

Qarshiyev Murod Narzullayevich

Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institute

School Management Teacher

Annotation: *In person-centered technologies, the student's personality is placed at the center of the pedagogical process, creating favorable conditions for his development and realization of his natural potential. Therefore, in modern technologies, the pedagogical process should be based on person-centered teaching technologies.*

Keywords: *person-centered education, learning technologies, methodology, teaching technologies, learning process.*

Education prioritizes self-determination, self-transformation, the discovery of human natural gifts, and the development of thinking skills in the activities and communication of students in ethics, professional skills, and activities. . In humans (especially children), there is a genetically inalienable need for self-awareness as an individual. Students need knowledge and skills on the subject, but not only goals, but also the most important means of self-development, self-action, self-determination. lim, by its very nature, envisages the full development of all participants in the educational process. Person-centered education directs the teacher to his students, to study them in detail, to get an idea of the nature of each of them, their interests, abilities. Provides an opportunity to explain the child's behavior and attitude to lessons, to choose forms and methods of educational activities, taking into account the characteristics, abilities and level of development of the child. The teacher recognizes the child's right to 'be himself', in his lessons the child finds himself in a 'successful situation'. This means that when designing education, of course, the approach should be based not on the personality of a particular learner, but primarily on the learning objectives associated with future professional activities. allows you to unify the unit process and achieve high efficiency.

The following are the basic principles of person-centered learning technologies:

- Humanism, that is, showing full respect and love to a person, helping him, looking at his creative abilities with confidence, completely renouncing rape;
- cooperation, ie democracy, equality, partnership in the relationship between teachers and students;
- Free upbringing, that is, giving a person the freedom and independence to choose his or her life activities in a wide or narrow range, resulting in internal feelings, not external influences. The communicative basis of person-centered technology is a human-personal approach to the student in the pedagogical process.

In person-centered learning, the teacher ensures that the self-transforming learner moves to a new state, creates the conditions, and transforms the process of self-transformation into cultural forms. It takes care of the student's understanding of the learning goals and objectives, their acceptance by the students, changes the definition of the learning task according to the needs of the students, In this process, the student expresses his / her opinion, which differs from the opinion of the teacher and other students, who have the right to make mistakes, and who clearly demonstrates his / her abilities. Disagreement between student and teacher is not seen as a resistance that needs to be broken. In this teaching technology, the attitude of pedagogy to the student is authoritarian, that is, in the process of learning it is manifested as a single subject, and students act only as an object.

In other words, in authoritarian teaching technology, the initiative and independence of the student is almost lost, and teaching is compulsory. The main unit of teaching in the classroom system of teaching, which is still the most widespread in the world, is a lesson, which is devoted to a single subject of a single subject and is led by a teacher. initiative and independence will fade away on their own.

Person-centered learning technologies mainly shape students' knowledge and skills, not personal development. It is obvious that traditional teaching technology, by its nature, does not fully meet the requirements of today's society for educational institutions. In contrast, in person-centered learning technologies, the national model of student education is at the heart of the pedagogical process, creating favorable conditions for its development and realization of its natural potential.

The main component of the national model of education - the individual, the state and society, continuing education, science, production - is the main component of the "person". In other words, the

entire education system, including teaching, must be focused on the individual student. At the same time, the volume, diversity, propensity and adequacy of information, the creation of the necessary conditions for the organization of effective individual and independent learning have become even more important. with the educator becoming his partner in terms of his attitude towards the student. The communicative basis of person-centered learning technologies is a human-personal approach to the student in the pedagogical process.

The main purpose of the new relationship is to abandon the pedagogy of violence, which is currently ineffective and unaccountable, because in the process of upbringing violence is impossible, punishment humiliates, oppresses, slows down its development. It is very important today to teach young people in the reformed educational institutions freely, without coercion, to show the essence of an individual approach to their personality.

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